

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

IMPROVING THE STRATEGY FOR INCREASING COMPETITIVENESS IN FOOD INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

The article discusses the implementation of systematic measures of further development of the practice of entering into cooperative relations between small enterprises through the food industry in the conditions of New Uzbekistan, and presents long-term strategic directions for the development of industrial cooperation. A three-block direction of the proposed strategy for increasing competitiveness has been developed.

Keywords. integration, strategy, competition, organizational and economic mechanism, innovative technologies, product quality, specialization, potential, management system, modern methods and techniques.

Introduction. According to the analysis of world practice, high competitiveness is being achieved due to the use of innovations in the activities of enterprises operating not only in the food industry, but also in other industrial sectors. We can see that the composition of the strategies consists of technical and technological modernization processes, vertical or horizontal diversification of product production at the enterprise, as well as appropriate measures to increase the innovative activity of the enterprise.

In the context of New Uzbekistan, priority is also given to the implementation of systematic measures to further develop the practice of entering into cooperative relations between small enterprises in the country's industry, including the food industry, and the following long-term strategic directions for the development of industrial cooperation have been identified: targeted attraction of business entities from all segments of the industrial products market, implementation of program measures by providing all interested circles with detailed information on the types, technical specifications and quality indicators of industrial products produced in the republic, and regular holding of industrial fairs; organization of the operation of an electronic cooperation portal as an important tool for finding partners, establishing economic, including long-term, cooperative relations, providing the opportunity to quickly and remotely conclude economic agreements (contracts) for the supply of industrial products; implementation of state support measures aimed at creating sustainable demand for local producers through the organization of technoparks and small industrial zones, and the public procurement system [1].

Literature review. According to the results of scientific research of recent years in the economic literature, by scientists such as K. Firlej [3], R.E. Gulev [4], M. Reeves [6], P. Suchanek [7], J. Zhang [8], N.R.

Khuseynova [5] devoted to the areas of increasing the competitiveness of food industry enterprises in different countries, it is necessary to develop strategies for increasing their competitiveness within the framework of enterprise development programs

Research methodology. The general strategy of economic development set out in the works of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Government resolutions, as well as foreign experience of scientists on issues of increasing the competitiveness of food industry enterprises in the republic's economy, as well as logical, monographic, scientific abstraction and comparative comparison methods were used.

Analysis and results. Taking into account the priority areas of development of industrial cooperation in the country mentioned above, and the fact that in world practice, priority is given to the use of modernization, diversification and innovation programs to increase the competitiveness of food industry enterprises, we believe that it is appropriate to use modernization, diversification and innovation programs in a balanced manner when organizing cooperation of food industry enterprises operating in small industrial zones.

In this respect, when organizing cooperation of local enterprises operating in small industrial zones in different regions of the republic, it is necessary to develop a general strategy for increasing the competitiveness of the cooperation, which is organized on the basis of the integration of enterprises for the production of a certain type of product.

According to the analysis of world practice, strategies for increasing the competitiveness of food industry enterprises have a structurally schematic structure, as shown in Figure 1, and should be constantly improved in proportion to the activities of the enterprise.

ness of enterprises by increasing their innovative activity which is required to be implemented in the following three stages:

the first, the stage of adoption of innovations - this involves the introduction of innovations by the enterprise into the economic activities of the enterprise by purchasing innovations used in the practice of leading enterprises in the world;

the second, the stage of innovation acquisition - in which, starting from the stability of the level of innovation activity of the enterprise due to the increased speed of adoption of innovations into its practice, practical measures are taken to fully adopt the innovative projects being introduced into its practice;

the third, the stage of innovation transfer - in which the enterprise, having fully mastered the innovations, has the opportunity to further improve them and achieve additional income by selling or licensing the innovations developed by it to other enterprises.

At the same time, ensuring the innovative activity of the enterprise can be in the following two directions:

- product innovation - this involves innovations by the enterprise to increase the level of profitability received from consuming the product based on a thorough study of the requirements of consumers in the market. Or the production of completely new types of products is also considered an innovation;

- technical or technological innovation - this involves innovations in the production technique or its technology by technical parks, higher educational institutions, scientific research institutes, or departments engaged in scientific and innovative activities established on the basis of enterprises. Enterprises that produce this type of innovation are usually large companies, transnational corporations.

In general, it is advisable to apply the proposed strategy for increasing the competitiveness of food industry enterprises in the activities of small industrial cooperatives. On the basis of this, the generalization of the development potential of small food industry enterprises in the form of integrated associations will ensure the successful implementation of the strategy for increasing the competitiveness of the enterprise. The following results will be achieved due to the application of the strategy for increasing the competitiveness of food industry enterprises in the activities of small food industry cooperatives established in the country:

- the production chain of products is fully mastered;

- the production of high-tech products is introduced, the quantitative and qualitative indicators of the products are improved;

- the relative and absolute advantage of local manufacturing enterprises in the international food industry markets is ensured, and the volume of exports of food products with high added value, considered ready for consumption, is increased;

- national food security is ensured, and the domestic consumer market is saturated with high-quality, inexpensive food industry products, etc.

Conclusions and proposals. It should be noted that in order to increase the level of global competitiveness of food industry enterprises, additional financial resources are needed in their activities as enterprises

leading the international food industry market have a significant advantage over local enterprises not only in terms of production, but also in terms of financial resources. Taking into account this situation, it is necessary to move to the practice of financing the competitiveness of local food industry enterprises by directing financial resources allocated by international financial organizations and institutions to the state extra-budgetary Export Support Fund in the following areas:

- for financing projects in the food sector aimed at creating a value-added chain from the production of products in the sector to their delivery to the consumer - for a period of up to 10 years with a 3-year grace period;

- for working capital - for a period of 18 months with a 6-month grace period;

- for financing pre-export and export-related trade operations of food exporting enterprises for a period of up to 2 years, with the volume of exports by them over the last 12 months:

from 100.0 thousand US dollars to 1.0 million US dollars - up to 100.0 thousand US dollars;

From 1.0 million to 2.0 million US dollars - up to 1.0 million US dollars;

From 2.0 million to 4.0 million US dollars - up to 2.0 million US dollars;

Allocation of financial resources from more than 4.0 million US dollars - up to 3.0 million US dollars.

We believe that the practice of allocating financial resources in the above areas should be carried out based on the following requirements:

- financial resources are provided in an amount not exceeding an annual rate of 4.0 percent (of which 2.0 percent is the bank margin);

- if, after the receipt of working capital by exporters, the export volume in the next year does not increase by at least 20 percent, the preferential loan will be reissued as a commercial loan;

- food processing enterprises and exporters are allowed to transfer up to 50,000 US dollars per year to foreign accounts without special decisions to establish trading houses and stores in foreign countries.

In general, the implementation of the strategy for increasing the competitiveness of local food industry enterprises based on the above proposals will allow the country to achieve the set of strategic goals and objectives to increase the level of global competitive advantage of the national food industry ahead of schedule.

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